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P. M. B. 1515,
ILORIN, NIGERIA**
geostudiesjournal@gmail.com

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CONTENTS

Issue 1

- ASSESSMENT OF INDIGENOUS AND MODERN AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES TO ENHANCE FOOD SECURITY IN MUBI NORTH L.G.A., ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA** 1 - 14
Danjuma I. Garandi, Abbas Bashir, Mohammed S. Dzarma, Nakama D. Falu, Shehu M. Baba, Jummai V. Zira, Hyelnacha B. Anthony
- YELLOW FEVER VULNERABILITY AND RISK PATTERN: A GEOSPATIAL ANALYSIS OF THE 2019 AND 2020 CASES IN BAUCHI STATE, NIGERIA** 15 - 36
Ishaq Aliyu Abdulkarim, Sulaiman Yunus, Yakubu Yunusa, Ismaila Ibrahim Yakudima
- PERCEPTION OF RURAL FARMERS ON THE EFFECTS OF LAND DEGRADATION ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY IN IMO STATE, NIGERIA** 37 - 47
Osuji U. T, Femi Martins Durumbah-Obih, Jonah M. C., Emeruwa A. M, Akande S. N, Udunwa N. B, Ugwunali E. J, Okoroafor U. N, Okenwa-Onuobia I. M, Obasi G.
- IMPACT OF CRUDE OIL SPILLAGE ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY OF RURAL FARMERS IN DELTA STATE, NIGERIA** 48 - 58
Osuji U. T, Emeruwa A. M, Akande S. N, Jonah M. C, Udunwa N. B, Ugwunali E. J, Obasi G., Okoroafor U. N, Okenwa-Onuobia I. M
- CORRELATE OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS INFLUENCING THE DURATION OF STAY OF IGBOMINA MIGRANTS IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA** 59 - 74
Paul, A. A, Awoyemi Olakunle, Paul, B. G, Omoniyi, L. L, John, A. O

Issue 2

- THE SCOPE OF DESERT ECOTOURISM ACTIVITIES IN THE BULATURA OASES SECTOR (BOS) OF CHAD BASIN NATIONAL PARK (CBNP) IN YOBE STATE-NIGERIA** **75 - 91**
Ofre, D. O, Sawa, B. A, Ummulkhair Hussaini, Okechukwu Oko, Neji, S. S, Achare, L. E, Ofre, S. U
- APPLICATION OF CA-MARKOV CHAIN MODEL IN LAND USE/LAND COVER PROJECTION IN SOUTHERN PART OF GOMBE, NIGERIA** **92 - 105**
G. O. Abu, R. D. Abu, H. L. Bizi
- ASSESSMENT OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF TOURIST ATTRACTIONS IN ODO-OWA, KWARA STATE, NIGERIA** **106 - 113**
Adekunle J. O., Adeniyi Adedapo
- SOIL FERTILITY STATUS AND ITS IMPLICATIONS ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY IN OKEOSE, ILORIN EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, KWARA STATE** **114 - 122**
Adeniyi Adedapo, Ajadi B. S., Banjoko A. L.

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Address:	Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.
Emails:	geostudiesforum@unilorin.edu.ng, edabijalt@unilorin.edu.ng
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ASSESSMENT OF SOCIO- ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF TOURIST ATTRACTIONS IN ODO-OWA, KWARA STATE, NIGERIA

Adekunle J. O.¹ and Adeniyi Adedapo²

¹Department of Tourism Management, Kwara State Polytechnic, Ilorin

²Department of Environmental Science and Management Technology, Kwara State Polytechnic, Ilorin

Abstract: This study assessed the socio economic impact of tourist attractions in Odo Owa, Kwara State, Nigeria. A total of 80 copies of structured questionnaire was administered to collect information on socio economic characteristics of respondents using simple random technique. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed in the analysis of the data. Percentages were used to explain the demographic and socio economic activities of the respondents while Chi Square was used to determine the relationship between the availability of attractions and the socio-economic development of the community. The result of Chi-Square shows that there is no significant relationship between the location of the tourism potentials and socio economic development of the people in Odo-Owa. The study shows that tourism activity has not contributed to job creation, increased income and improved quality of life of the people in the study area. In addition, tourism activity has not contributed to the development of infrastructural facilities in the area. The study recommends that the relevant private organizations and government agencies should be encouraged to promote tourism activities in the area. This encouragement can come in form of incentives such as tax rebate and physical development of the area

Key words: Assessment, Socio- economic, Tourism, Tourist, Attraction.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of the largest and fastest growing industries in the world. According to Lengnen et al. (2020) tourism is a significant contributor to national and local economies around the world. The significance of tourism can be understood when one considers the fact that it increases revenue, generates employment opportunities, encourages the private sector and develops infrastructure (Akighir, 2017). It is one of the economic activities that stimulates economic growth and development. Tourism has the potential to contribute positively to the socio-economic development of any contemporary society.

Tourism is an integral part of socio economic activities capable of generating income for the

people. According to Organización Mundial del Turismo, (2020) and World Travel and Tourism Council, (2021), prior to COVID-19 pandemic, tourism industry accounted for 10.4% of the global GDP and 10.6% of all jobs with an essentially constant growth trend over time. Tourism is seen as a growth industry since the flow of tourists to different tourist destinations contributes to economic growth (Bassi and Alfred 2018). The impact of tourism according to Bassi and Alfred, (2018) can be seen in tourism definition as given by World Tourism Organization (2015) which described tourism as an activity involving the travels of persons to places outside their usual environment for not more than once for leisure; this definition is thus indicative of how tourism activities may benefit host communities and

improve local economies in terms of provision of employment and a source of income. Charlie (2015), also reported that tourism creates employment opportunities for the people and brings in large amounts of income into a local economy in the form of payments of goods and services needed by tourists. The significance of this sector can be shown from the fact that it increases revenue, generates employment opportunities, encourages the private sector and develops infrastructure (Akighir, 2017). Tourism contributes immensely to the economic development of both developed and developing nations.

According to United Nation World Tourism Organization (2019) tourist attraction is a location, area or destination which can be natural, cultural, historical or man-made that people visit for leisure, interest or entertainment which often provides a memorable experience, education or inspiration. Tourist attractions generate significant value and socio-economic activities for host communities through visitors spending on accommodation, food, transportation, shopping and entertainment. These activities often lead to job creation, economic growth, infrastructural development, environmental sustainability and improved socio well-being of the host communities. Similarly, tourism is one of the driving forces for socio-economic development. Wang, Wang and Ning, (2020) opined that tourist attraction tends to experience greater economic development, as they attract more visitors, generate higher tourism revenues, and stimulate local businesses.

Tourism plays significant roles in socio-economic development of many nations. This is because it contributes towards alleviating the major political, social and economic problems that characterize the rural areas. In Nigeria, tourism has been playing a significant role in

the socio-economic development of the country. The physical and socio-cultural attraction features which are located across the country promote sustainable economic development. The ecological diversity and cultural variety in the nation also underscores the potential of tourism in promoting socio-economic development of the country. Tourism is a sustainable tool for achieving optimal employment opportunity and promotion of rural and urban integration. It also promotes, revenue generation for government and cultural exchange across the nations. According to Charlie (2015), tourism provides employment opportunities in the sector of the economy associated with tourism. Food vendors, souvenir sellers and retailers emerge automatically in tourist attraction centres because the tourist needs their services. Other service industries that benefit from tourism include transportation services (like airline, cruise, ships and taxi cabs), hospitality services (such as accommodations, including hotels and resorts), and entertainment venues (such as amusement parks, shopping malls, music venues, and theatres). Tourism provides employment opportunities both for the skilled and unskilled labour in the host community.

Tourism potentials in Nigeria are spatially located across all the thirty States and Federal Capital and revenue that can be generated from these centres are enough to make the country one of the foremost tourist destinations in the world. Just like other States, Kwara State is endowed with abundant natural and man-made socio-cultural resources that make it an appealing destination for tourist (A Tourist Guide of Kwara State Tourist Attraction Site, 2015). The tourist attractions in the State have the potential to boost the economy and raise the standard of living of the residents, most especially the host communities. Although Kwara state is blessed with abundant tourist attractions, a number of challenges pose as

threat to the development of tourism sector in the state. Such challenges include lack of awareness of tourist attractions and unavailability of infrastructural facilities such as good road network and electricity. Many people are not aware of locations of tourist centres in the state. In cases where the level of awareness is high, level of provision of infrastructural facilities by the government are low, hence the very little contribution of tourism sector to revenue generation and socio-economic development of the state. It is against this background that this study aims at assessing the socio-economic impact of tourism in Odo-Owa in OkeEro Local Government of Kwara State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to examine the impact of the tourism attractions on income generation, provision of employment and infrastructural development in the study area.

THE STUDY AREA

Odo Owa is one of the major towns in Oke-Ero Local Government Area of Kwara State. It is at the intercept of latitude $7^{\circ} 53'05''N$ and longitude $5^{\circ}04'11'' E$. Odo Owa is situated in crescent valley about 4km East of Omu Aran along Ilorin-Kabba express road with

neighbouring towns such as Osi, to the East, Etan and Erinmope to the South, Oko and Idofin to the North and Ilofa to the West (Ugwu, 2018). Figure 1 shows Odo Owa, the study area on map of Kwara State. The climate of the study area exhibits both wet and dry seasons. It is characterized by hot, humid season and a dry, cooler season. The wet season begins towards the end of April and last till October. The dry season begins in November and end in March Temperature in the region ranges between $25^{\circ}C$ and $37^{\circ}C$. The total annual rainfall is 1447.7mm. Rainfall in the area shows double maximal pattern. Odo Owa has tropical vegetation. Agriculture is the major economic activity of the people in the area. Most of the residents in the area are small scale farmers and they engage in the cultivation of cereal crops like maize, guinea corn, groundnut and tuber crops like yam and cassava. Traditional craft like blacksmithing and soap making and other industrial activities are also practiced in the area. In addition, there are traders, artisans and civil servants in the area. The major tourist attractions in the area are Olota's Palace, Adin and Black Soap Industry and Imoleboja Rock Shelter at Ipekun near Odo-Owa.

Figure 1: Map of Kwara State Showing Odo-Owa, the Study Area

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Primary data were used in this study. These data sets were on the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents and the impact of tourism attraction on their livelihoods. While the demographic characteristics examined include age, gender and marital status the socio-economic characteristics examined includes income, occupation, education, employment generation and infrastructural facilities. Simple random technique was used in administering the questionnaire to the respondents. This technique was adopted because it gives all the respondents equal chance of being selected. A total of 80 copies of questionnaire were administered. All the administered questionnaire was filled and returned. This implies 100% response rate. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed in the analysis of the data. Percentages were used to explain the demographic and socio economic activities of the respondents while Chi Square was used to determine the relationship between the tourist potential and the socio-economic development of the community in terms of increase in income, improvement in standard of living, provision of employment, and provision of infrastructural facilities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

The population traits of the respondents were presented in Table 1. As seen in Table1 the

highest number of respondents falls between 31 and 40 years old which represent 41.3%. In term of gender, male group has the highest number of 46 respondents which constitute 57.5% of the total number of respondents. Table 1 also indicates that 42 respondents are married, 23 respondents (28.8%) are single, 6 respondents (7.5%) are divorced while 9 respondents (11.3%) are widow. About 48.8% of the respondents are farmers, 26.3% are traders, 15.0% are civil servants while 10.0% are artisan. This implies that highest percentage of respondents are farmers. Other result of the survey as indicated in Table 1 reveals that 47.5% of the respondents have secondary education, 33.8% have primary education, 21.3% have tertiary education while 7.5% of the respondents have no formal qualification. This result implies that most of the respondents are literate. Also, from table, about, 3.8%, 15.0%, and 32.5% of the respondents have monthly income of between < ₦20,000, ₦21,000- ₦40,000 and ₦41,00 – ₦60,000 respectively while 46.3% and 3.8% of the respondents have monthly income between ₦61,000 – ₦80,000 and above ₦80,000 respectively. The number of respondents with monthly income between ₦61,000 – ₦80,000 was the highest while monthly income less than ₦20,000 was the least. This implies that the highest average income of the people in the area is within the current Nigeria minimum wage of ₦70,000 per month. However, the highest average income of the respondents cannot be considered as being enough for the people to be economically stable due to high cost of living in the country.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Age (Years)	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
< 10-20	12	15.00
21-30	25	31.3
31-40	33	41.3
51-60	6	7.5
61-70	4	5.0
Gender		
Male	46	57.5
Female	34	42.5
Marital Status		
Single	23	28.8
Married	42	52.5
Divorced	6	7.5
Widow	9	11.3
Occupational Status		
Trader	21	26.3
Farmer	39	48.8
Civil Servant	12	15.0
Artisan	8	10.0
Educational Status		
Primary School	19	23.8
Secondary School	38	47.5
Tertiary	17	21.3
None	6	7.5
Monthly Income		
< ₦20,000	2	2.5
₦21,000-40,000	12	15.0
₦41,000-60,000	26	32.5
₦61,000-80,000	37	46.3
Above ₦80,000	3	3.8

Source: Authors Computation, 2025

CONTRIBUTIONS TO JOB CREATION, INCREASE IN INCOME AND IMPROVEMENT IN THE QUALITY OF LIFE

Tourism has the potential to boost income and improve quality of life by creating jobs, increasing income and stimulating local

economies through spending on goods and services. The respondents were asked a yes or no questions about whether or not tourism has created employment opportunities and increased their income and quality of life. From Table 2, 90.0%, 95.0% and 97.5% of the respondents indicated that tourism

activities have no direct impact on job creation, their income and quality of life respectively. This implies that tourism has

not contributed to job creation, increased income and improved quality of life of the people in the area.

Table 2: Creation of Job, Increase in Income and Improvement in quality of life of the Respondents

	Creation of Jobs		Increase In Income		Improvement In Quality of Life	
	No	Percentage	No	Percentage	No	Percentage
Yes	8	10.0	4	5.0	2	2.5
No	72	90.0	76	95.0	78	97.5

Source: Authors Computation, 2025

TOURISM AND PROVISION INFRASTRUCTURE

Tourism provides various benefits to the host community, playing a critical role in the provision of infrastructures like good road, accommodation, and telecommunication. Table 3 present the response of the people to impact of tourism on provision of infrastructure

in the study area. Majority of the respondents, more than 96%, indicated that tourism has not contributed to the provision of good road, portable water, electricity, education, health care and improved communication network. This implies that tourism has not contributed to the development of infrastructural facilities in Odo Owa.

Table 3: Tourism and Provision of Infrastructure

Provision of Infrastructure	Yes		No	
	No	%	No	%
Good Road	1	1.3	80	98.3
Provision of portable water	2	2.5	78	97.5
Provision of electricity	0	0.0	80	100.0
Education e.g building of school/ classrooms	0	0.0	80	100.0
Health care facility (clinic or cottage hospital)	3	3.8	77	96.3
Improve communication (radio station telephone or mobile phone)	0	0.0	80	100.0

Source: Authors Computation, 2025

TOURISM AND COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT

Tourism is an effective tool for community development. It plays a crucial role in economic growth, infrastructural development, promotion of improved standard of living and promoting cultural heritage of the host

communities. Table 4 shows the response of the people on the impact of tourism on community development. The result of the survey, as indicated in Table 4, shows that about 98.5% of the respondents indicated that tourism has not contributed to the community development.

Table 4: Tourism and Community Development

Community Development	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Yes	2	2.5
No	78	98.5

Source: Authors Computation, 2025

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SPATIAL LOCATION OF TOURISM POTENTIALS AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Chi square statistics was used to examine the relationship between the tourism potentials and socio economic development in the host community. The result of the analysis shows that the value of Chi- square calculated is less than the Chi- square critical value. This therefore, implies that the null hypothesis (H_0), which states that there is no significant relationship between the location of the tourism potentials and socio economic development in Odo Owa was accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H_1), which states that there is a significant relationship between the location of tourism potentials and socio economic development was rejected. This implies that there is no significant relationship between the location of the tourism potentials and socio economic development in Odo Owa.

CONCLUSION

The study assessed the socio-economic impact of tourist attractions in Odo Owa, Kwara State. The results of the study show that tourist attraction has no impact on the socio-economic activities in the area. Tourism has not contributed to job creation, increased income and improved quality of life of the people in the area. Similarly, tourism has not contributed to the community development and development of infrastructural facilities in Odo Owa. The result of the Chi-Square analysis shows that there is no significant relationship between the location of the tourism potentials and socio economic development in Odo Owa. The results, therefore, imply that despite many tourism potentials and tourist attractions in the area, the people in the community have not benefited economically from tourism activities. In view of this, the study therefore recommends that both the private organizations and government should be committed to the development of tourism in the area. Government should focus on developing tourist sites, tourism facilities and provision of infrastructure in the area.

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